

SIMULATING THE MANUAL WHEELCHAIR FREE TURNING DECELERATION

Bascou J.^{a,*}, Sauret C.^b, Hybois S.^{a,b}, Villa C.^a, Lavaste F.^b, Pillet H.^b

^aInstitution Nationale des Invalides, Centre d'Etudes et de Recherche sur l'Appareillage des Handicapés, Woippy, France

^bArts et Métiers ParisTech, Institut de Biomécanique Humaine Georges Charpak, Paris, France

*Corresponding author: Bascou Joseph; joseph.bascou@invalides.fr

Abstract Adequate manual wheelchair (MWC) configuration is crucial for efficient MWC locomotion. Evaluating the effect of various configurations can be done through simulation, which relies on the definition of a mechanical model. The aim of this paper was to propose and evaluate a simplified mechanical model of a rolling and turning MWC. MWC decelerating motion following a rotational impulse was simulated based on MWC geometry, anteroposterior load distribution, and wheel and ground materials. Mechanical equations of a free rolling and turning MWC were obtained. Linear and angular accelerations were linked to geometric and inertial settings of the MWC and to the wheel mechanical behaviors. To evaluate this model, one MWC, loaded with fixed additional masses and instrumented with inertial measurement units, was accelerated in rotation and let decelerate freely. Ground and wheels materials were used to assess the wheel rolling and turning resistances parameters from literature data, whereas MWC inertial parameters and geometries were measured. These values were used as inputs for simulations. Evaluation of the simulation was performed by comparison between simulated and measured decelerations. Results show that the simulated and measured trajectories were close but that simulated angular decelerations were underestimated. Finally, if simulation of free moving MWC showed the link between settings, rotational and translational behavior, simplifications on the measurement process may have altered the accuracy of the simulations. This approach is nevertheless promising by shortening the process of setting selection and may have applications on energetic characterization, MWC setting optimization or occupational therapist training. Further works would focus on the extension of the mechanical model, in particular to include inclined surface and a moving MWC user.

Keywords manual wheelchair, mechanical model, simulation, turning movement

Introduction

The manual wheelchair (MWC) improves user's mobility and participation, but with a high physical cost, especially for the upper limbs. This results from a combination of inadequate environment (town, building), user strategy, or MWC configuration. In addition to the financial cost and technological limitations, a part of this unsuitability may be due to an incomplete understanding of the MWC specificities and behavior by the urbanists and the architects, and a difficulty for the MWC prescriber to assess the consequences of a MWC setting modification on the mechanical behavior of the MWC.

To help understand MWC locomotion, numerical simulation tools can play an important role. They could clarify the effects of various user characteristics and movements, MWC settings or environment characteristics on global energy expenditure, user joint stresses, etc... Numerical simulations can also be used within an optimization process, which would suggest a MWC configuration to the prescriber, guiding him in the final MWC choice.

Numerical simulations need a mechanical model, based on the MWC equations of motion, which includes a large panel of environments, users, settings and movements. This model needs to be fed by inputs describing the {MWC + user} geometry, mass and inertia and the wheel resistance to movement. The realism of a simulation is affected by the accurate assessment of these inputs. MWC geometry and weight distribution can be directly measured, whereas wheel/ground interactions can be assessed from literature (Sauret et al. 2011; Caspall et al. 2013; Lin et al. 2015; Fallot 2016).

As a first step, the purpose of this study was 1) to create a mechanical model of a MWC during a free turning deceleration; 2) to measure a real MWC movement, 3) to assess simulation inputs, to simulate the MWC movement and 4) to compare the real and simulated MWC movements.

Methods

To simulate the MWC movement, a mechanical model was created, with the following hypothesis: 1) the MWC translated and turned on a flat horizontal ground; 2) to ensure isostatic wheel/ground contact and to avoid load distribution hypothesis, the two front wheels and forks of a 4 wheeled MWC were considered symmetric and were represented as one sole fork/wheel; 3) the user was considered immobile with respect to the MWC and modeled only by his mass and inertia. No effort was produced on the rear handrims; 4) only ground resistances and gravity forces were considered as external forces; 5) MWC, wheel and fork mass and inertias were not neglected; 6) wheel individual rolling resistance and swiveling resistance were not neglected ; 7) no sliding movement was considered.

Kinematics and kinetics expressions of each solid composing the MWC were defined. Rolling resistance was modelled according to (Sauret et al. 2012). Wheel swiveling resistance was modeled according to (Fallot, 2016). Equations of motion were used to express the MWC linear and rotational accelerations as a function of the MWC solid velocities and the other inputs of the model (Bascou 2012). Runge-Kutta method was used to compute velocities from a timeframe to the next one.

For the experiments, one MWC (Ottobock Voyager) was loaded with a 40 kg additional masse (no additional weight was added for safety reason). One inertial measurement unit (IMU, Xsens) was placed on the additional masses and the MWC movements were measured with an optoelectronic system (Vicon, Oxford Metrics) based on reflective marker placed on the rear wheel pivots. Series (rotation clockwise and counterclockwise) of 5 trials were conducted on plywood and carpet. For each trial, the initial MWC rotation was imposed manually by an operator.

The loaded MWC geometry, center of mass and inertial parameters were measured with a tape measure, force-plates (AMTI) and a trifilar pendulum method (Hou et al. 2009), respectively. Rolling and swiveling resistance parameters were chosen from literature (Sauret et al. 2012; Fallot 2016).

The initial kinematic conditions for the simulation where the angular velocities, considering the linear velocity of the middle of the rear wheel axle to be null. The initial angular velocity was obtained from the IMU measurements, few instants after the beginning of the MWC free turning deceleration movement.

MWC Trajectory, mean angular velocities and decelerations of each surface were compared.

Results

MWC simulated trajectories were similar to the measured ones (Figure 1). Mean measured angular velocities ranged from 2.59 rad/s to 3.09 rad/s on plywood and carpet, respectively. Simulation results for these conditions exhibited differences of 24 and 32% with experimental data, respectively for plywood and carpet. Mean measured angular decelerations were 1.0 rad/s² for plywood, 1.5 rad/s² for carpet, their differences with simulation ranged from 24 to 38%. Simulation systematically underestimated angular deceleration, and consequently overestimated the angular velocities.

Figure 1: Example of MWC measured and simulated trajectories

Conclusion and discussion

The mechanical model designed for this study allows to simulate the movement of any configuration of a free moving MWC on horizontal ground. In addition, few inputs are required and can be determined with simple measurement equipments. The simulated kinematics reflected the MWC behavior and changed with the experimental conditions (plywood, carpet) although the accuracy should be enhanced. Experimental measurement inaccuracies, model assumptions, ground unevenness, generic ground interaction parameters, can partially explain the observed differences between measured and simulated results. Future work will focus on the model improvement, including inclined ground consideration, application of a propulsion force on the handrim and representation of the user's movements on the MWC.

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